

From Babbles to Speech

An In-depth review on the book Intercultural communication and language

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What do we speak?

All animals including humans have ways of communication. Evolution of language happened with parallel to the evolution of humans. From mere vocal sounds from early homo sapiens to complex languages consisting of words and phrases. It is the glue that holds the culture together. After all it is the first weapon drawn in a conflict.

According to Edward Sapir; Language is a purely human and non-instinctive method of communicating ideas, emotions and desires by means of voluntarily produced symbols.

When people embraced the wonders of the new world they started researching the roots of the beginning of everything. This science is called Anthropology. Although it is divided into 4 main parts as culture, society, biological and linguistics our main focus will be on Lingo culturology. It basically talks about the relationship between culture and Language.

How is culture connected with language?

Culture can be defined as the ideas, customs and social behavior of a particular people or society.

Language itself is a part of one's culture. One could debate that a language itself couldn't represent a culture and it would be an accurate statement. For example United States and United Kingdom both use English as their first language yet you wouldn't find much cultural similarities among the two. But the culture itself changed the language. That is why we have two variations of English (American English and British English) therefore it is evident that studying a culture teaches about the language.

Conflicts of cultures

If you were born and bred in a foreign country you belong to the culture of that specific country. In some cases some people try to persuade a foreign culture but that's a topic left for the future topics. So, when a person is grown in his/her specific culture it is hard for him or her to accept or cope with foreign cultures. Of course in the 21st century the world has become a global village exposing us to every other culture but in the ancient times when people weren't much open to the world other countries and cultures were totally alien to them. In ancient Greek and Rome, people from other countries were called Barbarians, the Greek word *barbarous* (alien) and in old Russian all foreigners were called *чужаки*. Therefore, clash of cultures was very common for a long time. What our ancestors warned us with their proverbs like "Act like a Roman when you are in Rome" or "Be and owl in the owl's wedding" basically describes us about cultural conflicts.

For example, in most Islamic countries such as United Arab Emirates public kissing, drinking or even indecent clothing can even get you jail time if you don't understand and agree to these cultural changes.

Often it is very hard to avoid these types of cultural clashes yet it could be reduced or even promote awareness via Intercultural communication and teaching foreign languages and culture.

Study and teaching of languages to overcome cultural clash

As mentioned earlier the key to dissect and explore a culture is through the language. The specific language of the specific culture. Study of the languages is more popular now than ever. Also, the invention of services like Google translate allows you to talk to foreigners even though you have never heard their language before.

But is it enough? Of course, electronic translators are not always efficient. It would be a long time until they will be intelligent enough to understand and translate natural conversations. In human language learning people study languages at school. For instance, a student whose first language is not English will study English at school. All the grammar rules, syntaxes, phonetics etc. and he/she will be fluent in it. In class rooms teachers even practice dialogues like 'How to book a hotel room, 'ordering food' etc. to teach the practical usage of the learned language. But is this learning process enough to explore a foreign culture? Speaking a language without no errors doesn't necessarily means he is now ready to blend in it with the culture. For example, we can try sending this above-mentioned student to the southern part of America. He will meet a local man from say Wyoming who would say *"howdy there partner"* (*'Hello friend'-a greeting often used by Southern Americans*) This uttered phrase is also English. But it is incomprehensible for a general English learner. Let us make the incident more user friendly. Send the student to a normal school in America with students who are same as his age. A classmate would ask him *"Hey dude holla at me after class. We finna go chill at my place"* (*'hey meet me after class. We are planning to go spend time at my house'- Commonly used slangs among teenagers*) These phrases are rather confusing to any person who just learned the language but didn't study the culture of the specific group. It also sometimes depends on the generation gap of the usage of language. Therefore, it is evident that study of language itself is not enough to blend with one person's culture.

Foreign students who study in Russia spends 10 months in a preparatory faculty studying Russian. But they always have a hard time in practical day today conversations with people due to the fact that most common people in Russia speaks very differently than what they learned in the faculty. Therefore, language is uniquely bonded with the culture and it is modified every day by people. This is why intercultural communication is comes very handy in the studying and teaching process.

Lost in the translation

If you use Google Translate to translate a phrase in a foreign language you will often get a direct translation (word by word translation), sometimes amateur language learners make this mistake too. This makes translations much harder. It could even cause more cultural issues. For an example a Russian speaker might say «недоперепил»

When broken down it usually means;

Не - not

До - up

Пере - over

Пил – drank

It could be translated as “*Not drank up too much*” in English it sounds ridiculous but there is no direct English meaning to this word. A few words like «хамство», «распутица», «авось» are also a few words which might make your Russian friend say “ну...я не знаю как сказать это по англиски”

In Sinhala we have lot of such words which don't have a specific English meaning mainly because Eastern cultures runs a long way before the invention of English and also because the approach of English was late for most Eastern cultures. (often until colonization or other factors)

In Sinhala language there are lot of such words which doesn't have a specific English meaning, mainly because Eastern cultures runs a long way before the invention of English and also because the approach of English was late. For example, the Sinhala word;

ස්ත්‍රීපය [ˈɪztuːiə] is translated as Pagoda in English but if you Google the word Pagoda you will get search results of photos of Pagoda's from different countries. Therefore, the word ස්ත්‍රීපය means very different in Lankan context and in other countries.

Sri Lanka use English as their 2nd official language the frequent usage of English words has given many different words that translate very differently from other English-speaking countries for example; the word ‘Cab’ usually means taxi in English but this word is also used to call a Pick-up truck. It is not unusual for a Sri Lankan to call their pick-up truck a ‘cab’.

Usually High schools in Sri Lanka are called colleges. For example, Richmond college, Mahinda college, All Saints college etc. and if a foreigner hears this, they would assume you are in a university or a higher education institute.

This shows the importance of the study of cultures when studying a language.

One can realize how deep this abyss of social conflict during his/her beginning of studies. Even a name can cause hundreds of problems when used in another culture. In Russian there is the first name, patronymic name and the last name. But in most other countries in west or east they don't use the father's name when writing their names. Although in some English-speaking countries they would use the father's first name and add Junior (Jr) to it. (ex: Robert Downey, Jr) Some people who have a middle name which was given to them at birth often struggle when filling out forms in Russia. Therefore, always the middle name is also considered as a part of the first name in writing leaving the middle name (patronymic part blank)

The variations of culture vs language do not limit to these syntaxes. Language is a mirror of the culture. It plays a role with concepts and real situations. Thus, it is a mirror to both real and cultural conceptual work.

Colors are encountered with our life every day. It is what makes our lives colorful, but they are simply just concepts. Colors are sort of like a mental image. It strikes a meaning when heard upon. When a English speaker hears the word 'blue' his brain makes a mental image of the color blue. If it was a German, he/she would imagine the color blue if someone says 'blau'. If the German didn't know English and the English person didn't knew German, neither of these two people will get a mental image of the color when it is said in the other foreign language.

Colors as a concept can be related to our daily lives in different ways. Thanks to colors you know when to stop at a red light, how to know if a fruit is ripe. Colors can be almost called as a universal part of the language when it comes to expressing ideas but it can differ from one culture to another. For example; in English we have two shades of blue as light blue and dark blue but in Mongolian they have two different names for the two colors respectively as 'Цэнхэр', 'хӨх'. Sometimes when the vocabulary is not enough to represent a color one would simply add a noun in order to represent his idea of the specific colors. i.e. in English someone would say Sky Blue, Navy Blue, Cornflower, cadet blue etc. But translating these words to another language would be extremely hard.

Another interesting factor about colors and language is that they can mean something more than just a color. (Homographs) For example the color 'Orange' also signifies the fruit. In Sinhala there are many Homographic colors such as 'කොළ' [kɔlɔ] means Green and also leaves of a tree (the more advanced/historical word is 'හරිත' [har:ðɔ] green color but it is not used in informal conversations). 'සුදු' ['sudu] means white also it is used to describe a fair person. If a person has a fair skin his skin tone is named as a 'සුදු' yet the direct translation of the word would be white therefore a lot of Lankan people would directly call a brown skinned person with fair skin complexion as a white person even though there is vast difference. (Currently a word called 'පැහැපත්' [pæhæpaðɔ] is used in describing a brown light skinned person). However still the people use the term 'සුද්දා' [su'dda:] (White skinned male) and 'සුද්දී' [su'ddi:] (White skinned female) when describing foreigners in informal speech. This is similar to the word 'Gringo' which is used in Spanish.

The major role played by colors in different cultures and their conveyed meaning is vast. In an American funeral people usually wear black as a sign of mourning, the tradition of wearing black at a funeral date backs to the Roman Empire. But in countries like Cambodia, Sri Lanka people wear white at funerals. In South Africa Red is the color of mourning while in China, Red is the color of happiness. In ancient Egypt Gold was the color of afterlife. This is why many tombs and pyramids have a lot of gold inside them. Universally a white flag means surrenders, in Sri Lanka the white flag is a representation of death. It is a custom to hoist a white flag when someone passes away. But if the deceased is a Buddhist monk people would usually decorate the coffin and hoist an orange flag. White flags and this color have affected so much with the lives of Sri Lankan people. If someone says "I almost saw white flags" It means he had near death experience.

In 1770 when Captain James Cook's ship hit the reefs in the north, they encountered kangaroos. He asked the Aborigines what it was and they had replied to him saying '*kangaroo*' which meant "I don't understand you" in Aboriginal language. However, this was not historically confirmed but is a good example for the language barrier incidents.

Modification of words

Languages develop rapidly with time. New words are added, old words are forgotten, words modify its meaning. Therefore, language cannot be called a uniform entity. Addition of new words started with the development of science and technology. Also, the 'borrowing' of words was also a significant feature. These types of words are called 'Loanwords' It was very notable during colonization. New cultures including the language was introduced. For example, in Sri Lanka, the Sinhala language has been modified with Dutch, Portuguese and English. i.e. the word

- Aberto – A Portuguese word - අර්බර්තු ව - Vacancy
- Garage – An English word - ගරාජය - Garage
- Kwitanite – A Dutch word - කුච්ඡාන්තිය - Receipt (квитанция – Also adapted to Russian from the Dutch word)

English is also sometimes a mixture of languages. Mostly European. Here are a few examples of 'borrowed' English words.

- Anonymous – **Greek** – *anonimos*
- Guru – **Sanskrit**
- Safari – **Arabic**
- Cigar – **Spanish**
- Ketchup – **Chinese** – *Kestiap*
- Entrepreneur – **French**
- Karaoke – **Japanese**

Semantic Changes

Words change their meaning over time. Word with a general meaning comes to have a more specific one, the process is called **Semantic narrowing**. An example is *deer* which once meant any kind of animal, but now means only members of the family *Cervidae*. The opposite process is **Semantic Widening**. Ex: the word *holiday* in old days only meant Religious days but now it is used in different ways. **Meaning shift** is also a notable thing which happened with time. For an example the word *Nice* meant Silly or foolish. Far different from the today's meaning.

